

Mapping macro- and microliter distribution in the Venice coastal area (Italy)

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Marine litter, in particular plastics, is a significant and growing marine contaminant that has become a global problem. Macro-litter is subject to fragmentation and degradation due to physical, chemical and biological processes, leading to the formation of micro-litter, the so-called microplastics. The purpose of this research is to assess marine litter pollution by using remote sensing tools to identify areas of macro-litter accumulation and to evaluate the concentrations of microplastics in different environmental matrices: water, sediment and biota (i.e. mussels and fish) and to contribute to the European project MAELSTROM (Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management). The aim is to monitor the presence of macro- and micro-litter at two sites of the Venice coastal area: an abandoned mussel farm at sea and a lagoon site near the artificial Island of Sacca Fisola; both sites are subject to strong anthropogenic pressure. The results showed that both study areas are characterised by high amounts of marine litter. However, as they are different contexts, the type of observed litter is also different. In fact, in the mussel farm area, most of the litter is linked to aquaculture activities (ropes, nets, mooring blocks and floating buoys), whereas in the Venice lagoon site the litter comes more from urban activities and from the city of Venice (car tyres, crates, wrecks, etc.). Microplastic is present in both sites and in all the analysed matrices. Generally, higher microplastics concentrations were found in the Lagoon site (i.e. in surface waters, mussels and fish). Moreover, some differences were also observed in shapes and colours comparing the two sites. These differences are related to the different types of macro-litter that characterised the two areas. The distribution of marine litter is therefore related to the main anthropogenic activities of the two areas such as fishery, aquaculture, tourism and waste management.